

Minimally Invasive Techniques for Managing Vesical Calculi**Parth Vadher¹, Sarthak Dhruv², Pinal Mehta³, Kautuk Patel⁴**¹Assistant Professor, Department of General Surgery, C.U. Shah Medical College and Hospital, Gujarat, India²MBBS, C.U. Shah Medical College and Hospital, Gujarat, India³Third Year Resident, Department of General Surgery, C.U. Shah Medical College and Hospital, Gujarat, India⁴Second Year Resident, Department of General Surgery, C.U. Shah Medical College and Hospital, Gujarat, India

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Abstract:**Background and Aim:** Vesical calculi are often associated with incomplete bladder emptying symptoms, although a combination of other urinary symptoms, such as terminal hematuria, suprapubic pain, weak stream, dysuria, etc., can also be present. Present study was done with an aim to evaluate the outcome of minimal invasive surgical procedure for vesical calculus.**Material and Methods:** The present study was conducted in the department of general surgery in a tertiary care hospital presenting with features of vesical calculus during the period of 1st January 2018 to 30 June 2019 in 30 patients. Collection of data is from clinical history, physical examination, relevant investigation and imaging modalities. Evaluation done on the basis of Post-operative pain, Hospital stays, Occurrence of infection, Cost effectiveness and Post op catheterization.**Results:** Males were more affected than females; alkaline reaction of urine favors UTI and stone formation. Commonly encountered organism in UTI was Escherichia Coli. X Ray KUB and Ultrasonography were the cost-effective methods to detect in patients who came with ureteric colic. Patients in whom calculi ranged from 2-4cm showed good results with spl. Patients in whom calculi ranged from 2-4cm showed good results with cystolitholapaxy.**Conclusion:** The Minimal invasive management of vesical stones is safe and practicable in majority of patients provided the pain and infection remain under control. Cystolitholapaxy is safe, simple and effective method of fragmentation of small sized stones and spl for medium to large size stone.**Keywords:** Cystolitholapaxy, Minimal invasive surgery, Ultrasonography, Vesical Calculi.

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Introduction

Urinary bladder is the temporary store house of urine which gets emptied through the urethra. The external urethral sphincter is the sphincter urethrae which are placed proximally in the wall of urethra, and not at the terminal part of the urethra. In the case of pylorus and anal canal, the sphincters are placed at their terminal ends. The male urethra subserving the functions of urination and ejaculation, i.e. expulsion of semen is 78-20 cm long with curvatures and comprises preprostatic, prostatic, membranous and longest anterior bulbar and penile parts. [1,3] The female urethra is for urination only and is 4 cm long. The catheterization if required is easier in the female than in the male. Clean and define the muscles, membranes and ligaments in the pelvic cavity. These are the levator ani obturator internus muscles; medial and lateral pubo prostatic ligaments and median, medial umbilical

fold. [4,5] Vesical calculi are infrequent in the female population, and the occurrence of a vesical calculus which weighs greater than 100g has rarely been reported in the literature. In the absence of predisposing factors such as urinary stasis or a foreign body, the aetiology of a vesical calculus becomes uncertain. Terminal gross hematuria with a sudden voiding stoppage is a common sign of a large bladder calculus. [6] Urinary calculi affect about 5-15% of the population in industrialized countries. [7] It is three times more likely to affect men than women. They almost always originate in the kidney and migrate to the ureter where they may grow. They often present with pain, haematuria or infection. Imaging of choice is non-contrast computed tomography (CT) of the kidney, ureter and bladder which is rapid and has a sensitivity of 99%. It had been noted that the

nephrolithiasis was mainly occurred in men than in women, however, this disparity of male to female ratio is declining recently. [4] Vesical calculi commonly occur secondary to urinary stasis but can also be seen, albeit infrequently, in healthy individuals without anatomic defects, foreign bodies, strictures or urinary tract infections. [8] Kumar et al reported a total vesical stone burden of 1400 gm, including. The 42 stones in a twenty-five-year-old male patient who underwent augmentation ileocystoplasty for pelvic fracture distraction urethral injury with concomitant rectourethral fistula. [4] Most of the giant vesical calculi have been reported in males. [9-12] However, in women, giant vesical calculi are very rare, possibly because of a shorter urethra and low prevalence of bladder outlet obstruction in comparison to men. [13]

Vesical calculi are often associated with incomplete bladder emptying symptoms, although a combination of other urinary symptoms, such as terminal hematuria, suprapubic pain, weak stream, dysuria, etc., can also be present. A common sign of a large vesical calculus is terminal hematuria with a sudden voiding block, but it is not universal. Although a distended bladder could be palpable in some cases, the stone per se is typically not palpable. Due to the lack of specific signs and symptoms, a definitive diagnosis without imaging or cystoscopy is not possible. [4] Certain systemic complications can occur in a later stage with giant vesical calculus, such as bilateral hydronephrosis and acute renal failure with resultant secondary effects of azotemia. Wei et al reported a 39-year-old man who presented with symptoms of azotemia and acute renal failure as a sequela of giant vesical calculus weighing 450 gm which was undiagnosed for ten years. [12] Present study was done with an aim to evaluate the outcome of minimal invasive surgical procedure for vesical calculus.

Material and Methods

The present study was conducted in the department of general surgery in a tertiary care hospital presenting with features of vesical calculus during the period of 1st January 2018 to 30 June 2019 in 30 patients. All the patients with all age group and both genders admitted with clinical diagnosis of "vesical calculus" under general surgery care in our institute will be taken as subjects for this study.

Inclusion criteria

- Patients who is willing to give informed consent. All cases presenting with stone in urinary bladder will be including in presenting study

Exclusion criteria

- Cases presenting with stones in urethra, ureter and kidneys.
- Patients with history of previous multiple abdominal surgeries.
- Patients with history of bladder surgery viz partial cystectomy, neo-bladder, neurogenic bladder.
- Patients not giving consent for surgery.

Collection of data is from clinical history, physical examination, relevant investigation and imaging modalities. Appropriate antibiotics was given according to urine culture and sensitivity report. Possibility of intra-operative conversion to other modality of Management from endourology procedure to open surgery was also being explained.

Endourological treatment via transurethral, percutaneous routes, were the options of management.

Evaluation done on the basis of

1. Post-operative pain
2. Hospital stays
3. Occurance of infection
4. Cost effectiveness
5. Post op catheterization

Statistical analysis

The recorded data was compiled and entered in a spreadsheet computer program (Microsoft Excel 2019) and then exported to data editor page of SPSS version 15 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA). Quantitative variables were described as means and standard deviations or median and interquartile range based on their distribution. Qualitative variables were presented as count and percentages. For all tests, confidence level and level of significance were set at 95% and 5% respectively.

Results

This study was done in 30 patients with all age group and both genders admitted in CU Shah medical college and hospital having urinary bladder calculi from 1st jan 2018 to 30th June 2019.

Table 1: Age wise distribution of cases

Age Distribution	
Age (Years)	Number
0-10	1
11-20	1
21-30	4
31-40	4
41-50	5

51-60	8
61-70	6
71-80	1
Total	30

3.33% patients belonged to age group 0-10, 11-20 & 71-80 each. 13.3% belonged to age group 21-30 & 31-40 each. 16.5% belonged to age group 41-50, 26.6% to 51-60 & 19.9% to 61-70 age group.

Table 2: Gender distribution of the patients

Procedure	Sex Distribution		Total
	Male	Female	
Cysto	11	4	15
Spcl	13	2	15
Total	24	6	30

Table 3: Distribution of cases according to Urine Culture

Culture	Number (n=30)	Percentage
Klebsiella	7	21.42
Proteus	5	16.66
E.Coli	5	16.66
Staph aureus	1	2.38
Pseudomonas	1	2.38

Klebsiella was the commonest 7 (21.42%) organism isolated, followed by proteus and E.Coli in 5 (16.66%) each and staph aureus and pseudomonas in 1 (2.38%) each. In the present study 12 (33.33%) of cases were anemic. Blood urea and Sr. creatinine were elevated in 9 (30.95%) of cases. Normal levels of serum calcium Sr. phosphate and serum uric acid was observed.

Out of 30 cases, 27 (92.85%) cases were identified by X-ray KUB 3 (7.14%) cases were radiolucent which were later detected by USG). 25 (92.3%)

cases were having solitary calculi and 2 (7.69%) cases were having multiple calculi in the bladder. (4 cases were associated with ureteric calculi and 2 cases were associated with renal calculi) Out of 30 patients 50% patients underwent cystolitholapaxy and 50% underwent spcl.

79.9% patients were male of which 45.8% cystolitholapaxy was done and 54.2% male spcl was done. 20.1% patients were females of which 66.7% cystolitholapaxy was done and 33.3% females spcl was done.

Table 4: Stone size wise distribution of cases

Variables	Cystolitholapaxy	1.5 cm	2 cm	Total	SPCL	3cm	3.5cm	4 cm	Total
Male	0	8	3	11	Male	4	7	2	13
Female	0	1	3	4	Female	0	1	1	2
Total	0	9	6	15	Total	4	8	3	15

In patients who underwent cystolitholapaxy neither male nor female patients had stone size less than 1 cm Males who went for cystolitholapaxy, 72.7% had stone size of 1- 1.5cm and 27.3% had stone size of 2cm. On the other hand 25% females had stone size of 1-1.5cm and 75% had stone size of 2cm. Males who went for SPCL, 30.8% males had stone size of 2-3cm, 53.8% had stone size of 3-3.5cm and 15.4% had stone size of 4cm. Females who went for SPCL, no females had stone size of 2-3cm, 50% had stone size of 3-3.5cm and 50% had stone size of 4cm. In the present study the hospital stay of patients undergoing SPCL was of 3 days whereas for patients undergoing cystolitholapaxy was of 2 days. Retention of urine was found in 6.7% patients in case of SPCL and 13.3% patients in case of cystolitholapaxy. UTI

was found in 20% cases in SPCL and 13.3% cases in cystolitholapaxy. Hematuria was mild and spontaneously clears within 24 hour found in 6.7% cases in SPCL and 13.3% cases in cystolitholapaxy. Burning Micturition was found in 20% cases in SPCL and 13.3% cases in cystolitholapaxy. Stricture was not found in cases of SPCL whereas 6.7% cases of cystolitholapaxy had stricture. Similarly, Urinary stream was not affected in cases of SPCL whereas in 6.7% cases of cystolitholapaxy urinary stream was affected.

Discussion

3.33% patients belonged to age group 0-10, 11-20 & 71-80 each. 13.3% belonged to age group 21-30 & 31-40 each. 16.5% belonged to age group 41-50, 26.6% to 51-60 & 19.9% to 61-70 age group. In

Mehdiratta et al [14] series. The maximum incidence 55.88% has been found in the age group below 10 years. In Anderson et al [15] series the peak incidence is at age group of 5 year, while 59.4% are below 10 and 68.7% below 15 years. In American series it appears that maximum age incidence of bladder stones in America is from 50-80 suggesting strongly that they are secondary to other pathology especially prostate enlargement of the prostate. In Kabra et al series the maximum number of bladder stone occurs in 1st decade of life (58%). In present study and studies conducted elsewhere shows that bladder calculi are common in male patients. It is tempting to suppose that low incidence of bladder stones in female children is due to the short and wide urethra so that small stones are passed before they give symptoms.

Calcium oxalate crystals were present in 26.66 % of the patient's indicating excessive salts, which form either the nucleus or the covering of the calculus. Culture showed no growth in 43.33% of the cases. 30% of the cases were positive for E.Coli. Klebsiella and proteus was present in 10% and 8.33% of cases respectively. Pseudomonas was seen in 8.33 % of the cases. They being urea splitting organisms produce alkaline urine and phosphate calculi. Our results resembled with Joel Gustavo et al [17] and Jan Hizbullah et al [18]. Leucocytosis was present in 18% of the cases. Blood urea raised in 6.6 % patients. Serum creatinine was raised in 8% of the cases. Anemia was seen in 22% of the patients. These results matched with Sandhya et al.

Males who went for cystolitholapaxy, 72.7% had stone size of 1- 1.5cm and 27.3% had stone size of 2cm. On the other hand 25% females had stone size of 1-1.5cm and 75% had stone size of 2cm. Males who went for SPCL, 30.8% males had stone size of 2-3cm, 53.8% had stone size of 3-3.5cm and 15.4% had stone size of 4cm. Females who went for SPCL, no females had stone size of 2-3cm, 50% had stone size of 3-3.5cm and 50% had stone size of 4cm. Nugroho et al reported a case of giant vesical calculus weighing approximately 800 gm in a male patient who presented with recurrent urinary tract infections for two years. [11]

In our case, the patient presented with predominantly storage lower urinary tract symptoms with no voiding symptoms or visible hematuria. This led to her being treated empirically for uncomplicated acute cystitis on multiple occasions and refrained her from seeking further medical care due to temporary symptom relief. Some studies have shown that the combined treatment method of RIRS with PCNL had higher SFR than the PCNL alone treatment in a single session. [19] Many urologists would suggest that open cystolithotomy should be performed through a small incision without postoperative catheter

drainage, as an outpatient procedure or with an overnight hospitalization. This approach would further decrease any advantage that the more complex endourological procedures might offer.20

Conclusion

The Minimal invasive management of vesical stones is safe and practicable in majority of patients provided the pain and infection remain under control. cystolitholapaxy is safe, simple and effective method of fragmentation of small sized stones and SPCL for medium to large size stone. However, the ultimate goal of treating vesical stones by whatever means is to get the patient stone free and prevent recurrence.

Intracorporeal lithotripsy with cystolitholapaxy is the most effective choice for small sized stone and spcl for medium to large sized stones majority of vesical stone are now treated by minimally invasive techniques. Imaging and ultrasonography plays a central role in both diagnosis and planning therapy for these patients of vesical calculi. Treatment modality depends on the stone size and composition, efficacy of each modality and associated morbidity, equipment available, surgeon's skill, patient's health.

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